

Diya'u al-Ta'aweel fee Ma'ani al-Tanzeel (The Bright interpretation of the meanings of the Qur'an)

also known as “ضياء التأويل في معاني التنزيل”

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Entry tags: Qur'anic commentary (Tafsir), Religious Group, Text, African Religion, Shari'a, Islamic Traditions

Tafsir by Sheikh Abdullahi ibn Fodio. Sheikh Abdullahi ibn Fodio was born in the year 1179 AH/1766 C.E. He wrote over one hundred and seventy books, covering a wide range of topics and issues of concern to the Muslim Ummah. He wrote his well known tafsir "Diya'u al-Ta'aweel fee Ma'ani al-Tanzeel" in the early 19th Century.

Date Range: 1766 CE - 1828 CE

Region: Gwandu

Region tags: Africa, Nigeria

One of the two capitals of the Fulani Empire

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: ابن فودي، عبد الله، (ن، د) ضياء التأويل في معاني التنزيل
- Source 3: Katsina State Library

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: noor-book.com/en/m5rfg
- Source 1 Description: Noor Book e-library
- Source 1 URL: <https://madanitimbukti.wordpress.com/2010/08/12/scholarship-and-revolution-an-examination-of-the-impact-of-a-tradition-of-tajdid-on-the-sokoto-caliphal-leader/>
- Source 1 Description: Bugaje, U. (2010). Scholarship and Revolution: An Examination of the Impact of a Tradition of Tajdid on the Sokoto Caliphal Leader. Madani Timbukti Traditions: A Traditional Approach to the Study of Islam. Wordpress.
- Source 2 URL: https://www.nigeriagallery.com/Nigeria/States_Nigeria/Kebbi/Abdullahi-Fodio-Tomb.html

- Source 2 Description: NigeriaGalleria. (2016). Abdullahi Fodio Tomb Kebbi State. Galleria Media Limited.
- Source 3 URL: https://web.facebook.com/JaizBankPlc/photos/a.574625162596716/2477515835640963/?type=3&_rdc=1&_rdr
- Source 3 Description: Jaiz Bank Plc. (2019). Historic tomb of Abdullahi Fodio. Facebook.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: noorbook.com

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Printed with moveable type

Notes: The document was made on four volumes: Volume 1 contained 263 pages, started from the first chapter of Suratul Fatiha to the last verse of fifth chapter (Suratul An'am. Volume 2: contained 244 pages, started from the sixth chapter (Suratul A'raf) to the eighteenth chapter (Suratul Isra). Volume 3: was made on 272 pages, started from the nineteenth chapter (Suratul Kahaf) to the thirty-fifth chapter (Suratul Fadir). Volume 4: made on 304 pages, which started from the thirty-six chapter (Suratul Yaseen) to the last chapter of the Qur'an (Suratu Nas) and brief conclusion of the whole Tafsir.

Number of sheets

- Single sheets

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Paper

Specify type of paper

- Specify: Normal white paper

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Ritual preparation

Notes: The document was modified with the additional biography of the author (Sheikh Abdullahi bn Fodio) and introductory comment on the Tafsir

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

- Physical preparation

Notes: The actual content of the Tafsir was not modified

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Notes: The reproduced copies are kept at various libraries and is available at markets for individual purchase

↳ Tomb

– No

↳ Cemetery

– No

↳ Temple

– No

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– Yes

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– Yes

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: It was stored in public libraries and copies are possessed by many individuals

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: The polity funded the text indirectly for his position as the leader (Sultan) of the first section of the emirate after the retirement of the Uthman bn Fodio from the administration

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– No

Notes: Most of the scholars at that time did their work voluntarily and for the development of Islamic scholarship, unless on a request by a government, so such funding could come up.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

Notes: In this case, there might be partial support by the polity to support scholarship

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– Yes

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– Yes

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– Yes

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

Notes: Those in the production team are not exempted from any tax to support them in the

publication of the text

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

↳ Present full-time?

– Yes

↳ Present part-time?

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Normally, are the disciples of Sheikh Abdullahi ibn Fodio, who are mostly among the Fulani ethnic group

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– Yes

↳ Is this class/caste based on a cultural status?

– No

↳ Is this class/caste based on socioeconomic status?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– Yes

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– No

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Yes

↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– I don't know

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– No

Notes: The author is not Arab by origin but rather belongs to the Fulani group which has a distinct language

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Notes: The language of the text does not belong to them

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– No

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– Yes

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Divinity

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– Yes

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– Yes

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text
This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.
–Total audience: 2000000

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)
–Number: 20000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience
–smallest audience: 20000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience
–largest audience: 1000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size
–Specify: religious

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)
–Number: 20000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience
–smallest audience: 1000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience
–largest audience: 2000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size
–Specify: conversion of others to the religion

↳ Nature of audience
[select all that apply]
– Large religious group (unknown relationship to other religious groups, or presence of other religious groups unknown)

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?
– No

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

Notes: They continuously convert many the traditionalist to the religion of Islam

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– No

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– Yes

↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of the fact that the text is silent on the matter?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of sanctions on such activities by the text?

– Yes

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: The group is considered a revivalist of the Islamic religion in the Hausa region of the west Africa

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it visible?

– Yes

↳ Is it hidden?

– No

↳ Can it be touched?

– Yes

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?

– No

↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve a protective function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve a healing function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?

– No

↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?

– No

↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?

– No

↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?

– No

↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?

– No

↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?

Please specify the substances in the sub-questions

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

Notes: Designed frame was made on the front page of every volume of the Tafsir

↳ Calligraphy?

– No

↳ Illustrations?

– Yes

↳ Illuminations?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The text is one among the bunch of Tafsir made on the Qur'an

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text was prepared on four volumes

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Vocabulary

Notes: It contained prose and Arabic poems quoted to support interpretations made on some verses

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

Notes: Various legal codes stated by some verses of the Qur'an were expatriated in the text, together with different opinions expressed by different scholars of Islam

↳ Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is there an institutionalized police force whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

↳ Is there an institutionalized judicial system whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

↳ Does the text in question specify institutionalized punishment?

– Yes

↳ Execution?

– Yes

↳ Exile?

– Yes

↳ Corporal punishments?

– Yes

↳ Ostracism?

– No

↳ Seizure of property?

– Yes

↳ Are there any established institutionalized rewards specified in the text?

– Yes

↳ Grants of property?

– Yes

↳ Social promotion?

– Yes

↳ Financial rewards?

– Yes

↳ Implied financial rewards (tax exemption)?

– Yes

↳ Grants of labor?

– Yes

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

Notes: The text is in support and formulation of Hijrah calendar, widely used in the Muslim communities

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Lunar?

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

↳ Planting?

– Yes

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

↳ Harvest?

– Yes

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– Yes

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– Yes

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– No

↳ Marriage?

– Yes

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– Yes

↳ Divorce?

– Yes

- ↳ Warfare?
 - Yes

- ↳ Funerary services?
 - Yes

- ↳ Trade/commerce?
 - Yes

- ↳ Festivals?
 - Yes

 - ↳ Frequency of festivals?
 - Specify: weekly festival of Friday Prayer,, annually festivals of Id-Prayer

 - ↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?
 - All members
 - Elites
 - Non-elites

 - ↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?
 - number: unlimited

 - ↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?
 - Yes

 - ↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population?
 - No

- ↳ Pilgramages?
 - Yes

 - ↳ How strict are the stipulations regarding pilgrimage?
 - obligatory for some

↳ Is encouraging pilgrimages a primary reason for the existence of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are pilgrimages guided by the text associated with particular life events?

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage guided by this text involve/follow major routes/roads?

– No

↳ Is the pilgrimage conducted by walking or by other means?

– Yes

↳ Feasting?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The spiritual nature of the Angels and jinns was mentioned in the text

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Yes

↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?

– Generally positive

↳ If associations with mental aggregates are neither positive or negative, are there other important details to know?

– Specify: Not really clarified in the text

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Notes: They distinguished them right from their creation, as corporeal was created from the clay while incorporeal was either created from light or fire

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– I don't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text expatiated the life to happen after death, which a particular chapter was titled the day of judgment

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: There is life to happen in the grave where the dead personality awaits judgment and the other one after judgment where successful shall enjoy in paradise while sinners shall suffer punishment in the Hellfire, as stated in page 229

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

Notes: The time and date were not specified in the text

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: it indicated the proper manner of washing and burying the corpses according to the guidance of Islam as pointed out in chapter five of the Qur'an

↳ Cremation?

– No

↳ Mummification?

– No

↳ Interment?

– Yes

↳ Cannibalism?

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?

– No

↳ Feeding to animals?

– No

↳ Secondary burial?

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse?

– No

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?

– No

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– Yes

Notes: It described two graves good for burial, which is incisional and other having slit

↳ Personal effects?

– No

↳ Valuable/precious items?

– No

↳ Other grave goods?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: It was stated in verse thirty-one of chapter five

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

Notes: the text did not direct for cenotaphs as all believers are considered the same hence preference is shown to any above others

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

Notes: The text stated a cemetery where dead bodies should be buried

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: Bathing and funeral prayer

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Bathing and shrowding of the dead body are pointed out in the text

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Notes: The supreme God was described as the only deity worth worshipping both in the world and the sky

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

Notes: A statement was made to describe him as unquestionable in His acts and deeds. Qur'an 21:23

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

–Specify: Majestic and all knowing

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - No
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - No
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - No
- ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - No
- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - No
- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - No
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
 - Notes: He rewards those to have done good deeds with eternal life in the hereafter

↳ Can punish

– Yes

Notes: He also punishes those to have done evil in the hereafter by casting them in the Hellfire

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– No

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

Notes: He does not eat, hence not in need of food

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: power to control everything

Notes: He exhibits features through his power to control everything in the world

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

|

- ↳ In waking, everyday life
 - No
- ↳ In dreams
 - No
- ↳ In trance possession
 - No
- ↳ Through divination practices
 - No
- ↳ Only through religious specialists
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living
 - No
- ↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
 - Yes
- ↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?
 - No
- ↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?
 - No
- ↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?
 - No

- ↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).
 - Yes

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

- ↳ Human spirits can be seen
 - No

- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt
 - No

- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world
 - Yes

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No

- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes

- ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - Yes

- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - No

- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - No

- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - No

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

–Specify: No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Jinns and angels are other supernatural beings that are present apart from human beings

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - No
 - ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: Jins and devils communicate to the evil doers to deluge them from the right fath, while Angels communicate to the Prophets and Messengers on the directives of Allah

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
 - Specify: Jinns could attack person

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Mysterious?

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular
 - Yes

- ↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: yes

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group

– Yes

↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?

– No

↳ Other form of punishment

– Specify: Burning in the hellfire

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified

– Yes

↳ Coming in this lifetime

– Yes

↳ Coming on a specified date

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future

– Yes

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ Coming has already passed

– No

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– Yes

↳ Other purpose

– Specify: He is a messenger sent by Allah to the christian adherents

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Yes

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– Yes

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ At some other time [specify]

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

- ↳ Divine judgment event
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world
 - No
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - Yes
- ↳ Other form of eschatology?
 - Specify: paradise, hellfire
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
 - No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

- ↳ What is the nature of this distinction?
 - Present & clear

- ↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?
 - Yes

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– No

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

– No

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– No

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
– Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
– Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
– Yes
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
– Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
– Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
– Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
– Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
– Yes
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
– Yes
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
– Yes

- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical)
– Yes
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
– Yes
- ↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– Yes

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 2

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Number of participants: 100

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Hours: 168

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

- ↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?
 - No
- ↳ Are there material offerings present?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they mandatory?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?
 - No
 - ↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')
 - No
 - ↳ Other?
 - Specify: none
- ↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?
 - Yes
 - ↳ By the community?
 - Yes
 - ↳ By specific individuals?
 - No

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it required?

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)?

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions?

– No

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: volantery services

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Notes: The group established the Sokoto caliphate in the Northern Nigerian region

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– Yes

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– No

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherent's interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– Yes

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– Yes

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– Yes

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

- ↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?
– Yes
- ↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?
– Yes
- ↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?
– Yes
- ↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?
– Yes
- ↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?
– Yes
- ↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?
– Yes
- ↳ Other form of regulation of public works?
– Specify: it advocate sincerity in public work and services

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Yes

- ↳ Does the text require the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes?
– Yes
- ↳ Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?
– No
- ↳ Is taxation linked to an understanding of charitable giving?
– Yes

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– Yes

↳ Power to conscript?

– Yes

↳ Maintain a full-time military corps (E.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

↳ Maintain a standing army?

– Yes

↳ Particular types of training/readiness?

– Yes

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Yes

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– Yes

↳ Characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]

– Large-scale agriculture (E.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards